

DOI: 10.31866/2617-2674.6.2.2023.289314

**MASTER'S PHOTO ART PROJECT
"MANIFESTATIONS OF THE SACRED ZAPORIZHZHIA"**

Vitalii Zaporozhchenko^{1a}, Oleksandra Sydorenko^{2a}

¹ Honoured Artist of Ukraine, Professor;

e-mail: kinomaestro@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0002-6027-456X

² Master's Student of the Cinema and Television Arts Department;

e-mail: alexandrasidorenko97@gmail.com; ORCID: 0009-0001-2960-4655

^a Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv, Ukraine

**МАГІСТЕРСЬКИЙ ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ
«ПРОЯВИ САКРАЛЬНОГО ЗАПОРІЖЖЯ»**

Віталій Запорожченко^{1a}, Олександра Сидоренко^{2a}

¹ заслужний діяч мистецтв України, професор;

e-mail: kinomaestro@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0002-6027-456X

² магістрантка кафедри кіно-, телемистецтва;

e-mail: alexandrasidorenko97@gmail.com; ORCID: 0009-0001-2960-4655

^a Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв, Київ, Україна

The author's idea of the master's photography project was to recreate the unique atmosphere, sacred and historical spirit of Khortytsia Island, where the symbol of the Ukrainian Cossacks, the Zaporizhzhia Sich, was located. For every nation, its history is essential, and Khortytsia has been preserving the heritage of our people for many centuries. At all times, the island has been attractive not only for its beauty but also for its sacred meaning. Nowadays, Khortytsia is not often depicted in cinematic works. Therefore, the relevance of the work is due to the need to draw the cinematographic community's attention to the historical and sacred heritage of this Cossack Island.

The representation of Khortytsia does not always reflect the historical and cultural aspects of this sacred place. Often films portray the island as a beautiful natural area without paying due attention to its cultural and historical significance for the Ukrainian people.

Audiovisual works can treat Khortytsia only as a landscape for filming, without resorting to a detailed study of the cultural heritage. The cinematography does not always succeed in accurately conveying the character and appearance of the island's sanctity, which can cause misconceptions among viewers.

The project aims to reflect the mystery, mysticism, and spirituality of these places through the language of photography. The photographs demonstrate different historical periods, starting from the Bronze Age (Braharnya sanctuary), the Cossack period (a series of Zaporizhian Sich images), and up to the present day, showing the evolution of humanity and its impact on the world.

The photo art project "Manifestations of Sacred Zaporizhzhia" is an informative, emotional, and visually exciting journey into the past that will inspire viewers to a deeper understanding of Ukrainian culture. The aim of the project is to reveal the depth of sacred Zaporizhzhia through photography, allowing viewers to immerse themselves in its mysteries, spirituality, and history, to see the diversity of this region and its impact on the cultural heritage of Ukraine.

Location address: Zaporizhzhia, Khortytsia Island.

Photographer: Oleksandra Sydorenko, alexandrasidorenko97@gmail.com.

Photo No. 1

**"Invitation to Sich"
from the master's
photo art project**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

24 mm | F5.6 | ISO 100 | 1/125 s

Image No. 1 editing with

Snapseed:

- Edit highlights and shadows
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 2

**"Church" from the master's
photo art project**

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F9 | ISO 100 | 1/320 s

**Image No. 2 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Edit highlights and shadows
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 3

**“Cossack hut”
from the master’s
photo art project**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

18 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

Image No. 3 editing with

Snapseed:

- Editing brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 4

**“Cannon”
from the master's
photo art project**

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
32 mm | F7.1 | ISO 100 | 1/200 s

**Image No. 4 editing with
Snapseed:**

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction
- Framing

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 5

**“Bell Tower”
from the master’s
photo art project**

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 5 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Edit the brightness and shadow areas
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 6

284

"Cart" from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F5.6 | ISO 100 | 1/125 s

**Image No. 6 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Edit the brightness and shadow areas
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 7

285

**"Fishing net"
from the master's
photo art project**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

48 mm | F6.3 | ISO 100 | 1/160 s

Image No. 7 editing with

Snapseed:

- Edit the brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 8

286

"Wheel"
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

38 mm | F7.1 | ISO 100 | 1/200 s

Image No. 8 editing with

Snapseed:

- Edit the brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 9

287

**“Church”
from the master’s
photo art project**

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F9 | ISO 100 | 1/320 s

**Image No. 9 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Edit brightness and shadow areas
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 10

288

"Hayloft" from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 10 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Editing highlights and shadows
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 11

**"Domes"
from the master's
photo art project**

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 11 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Editing highlights and shadows
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 12

290

"Hayloft"
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

28 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

Image No. 12 editing with

Snapseed:

- Editing highlights and shadows
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 13

"Hut"
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F6.3 | ISO 100 | 1/160 s

**Image No. 13 editing with
Snapseed:**

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction
- Remove unnecessary detail

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 14

292

"Zaporozhian Sich" from
the master's photo art project

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 14 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Editing highlights and shadows
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 15

**"Fence" from the master's
photo art project**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

32 mm | F10 | ISO 100 | 1/400 s

Image No. 15 editing with

Snapseed:

- Editing highlights and shadows
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 16

294

"Sanctuary"
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

18 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

Image No. 16 editing with

Snapseed:

- Editing highlights and shadows
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 17

**"Sanctuary Braharnia. Ritual circle"
from the master's photo art project**

295

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

18 mm | F6.3 | ISO 100 | 1/160 s

Image No. 17 editing with**Snapseed:**

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction
- Framing

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 18

296

"Sanctuary Braharnia"
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

24 mm | F5.6 | ISO 125 | 1/250 s

Image No. 18 editing with

Snapseed:

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 19

297

"Path"
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F7.1 | ISO 100 | 1/200 s

**Image No. 19 editing with
Snapseed:**

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 20

"River"
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens

Samsung SM-M315F
smartphone camera with built-in optics

Settings:

1.4 mm (35 mm equivalent: 13 mm) |
F2.2 | ISO 40 | 1/2004 s

Image No. 20 editing with

Snapseed:

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 21

299

**"Ceramic lamb"
from the master's
photo art project**

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:
18 mm | F7.1 | ISO 100 | 1/200 s

**Image No. 21 editing with
Snapseed:**
• Edit brightness and shadow areas
• Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 22

300

“Jug”
from the master's
photo art project

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

55 mm | F7.1 | ISO 100 | 1/200 s

Image No. 22 editing with

Snapseed:

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction
- Framing

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 23

**"Symbol of unity, honour and dignity"
from the master's photo art project**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3100 /
AF-S DX NIKKOR 18-55 mm VR

Settings:

55 mm | F11 | ISO 100 | 1/500 s

Image No. 23 editing with

Snapseed:

- Edit brightness and shadow areas
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

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